

Exploring the Financial Dimensions of Quantile-on-Quantile Regression: A Bibliometric Study of Emerging Research

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Abstract

Quantile-on-quantile regression (QQR) is an emerging technique in time series analysis. Since its inception in 2015, QQR has been widely used in different fields such as economics, environmental studies, business, and finance to show the quantile-dependent asymmetric relationship between variables. However, research papers on QQR are fragmented, hindering researchers from staying updated on influential works. This paper undertakes a bibliometric analysis to highlight several important indicators of the research trend in the QQR method. It analyses the research trend, seminal works, impact measures, collaboration network, authors' and journals' performance, and fields in which QQR is widely applied. Additionally, we discuss the improvements made to the QQR method over time. Furthermore, this paper highlights the shortcomings of ongoing research on QQR. By offering a comprehensive overview of the literature specifically finance literature, this study aims to serve as a reference point for future researchers and practitioners interested in applying or advancing QQR methodology across diverse domains.

Keywords: Quantile-on-Quantile Regression, QQR, advancement of QQR, limitations of QQR, Bibliometric analyses.

JEL classification: C14, C18, C50, C80.

1. Introduction:

Originally, quantile-on-quantile regression (QQR) was developed by Sim and Zhou (2015) in time series analysis to demonstrate the quantile-dependent relationship between oil price shocks and stock returns. Since its inception, however, QQR has found wide application across various branches of economics, environmental studies, business, and finance, revealing quantile-based asymmetric relationships between variables. QQR's strength lies in its ability to capture nonlinear effects on both sides of the specification. Unlike its precursor, quantile regression (QR), which illustrates how different quantiles of the dependent variable are affected by the independent variable, QQR, as introduced by Sim and Zhou (2015), for the first time enables exploration of the relationship between different quantiles of both dependent and independent variables.

The literature on QQR is expanding rapidly, yet research outcomes remain fragmented, making it challenging for researchers to stay abreast of influential studies in the QQR literature. To address this issue, a bibliometric analysis is conducted in this research paper on QQR methodology, aiming to elucidate prevailing research trajectories, seminal contributions, influential authors, and discernible patterns within relevant research domains and thematic frameworks. Quantitative bibliometric analysis examines bibliographic data to detect patterns, trends, and effects in study fields (Donthu et al., 2021). Characterised by

objectivity, it is a sophisticated literature analysis and information mining tool able of managing large-scale unstructured data (Xie et al., 2020). Bibliometric analysis investigates variables such citations, publication counts, collaboration networks, and the co-occurrence of various research keywords, which are vital proxies for assessing the quality and number of publications. This kind of study gives an impartial evaluation of bibliographic data, therefore enabling academics and legislators to find the most important scholarly publications in policy creation and academic research. Moreover, it helps writers to get a whole perspective on the field of study, spot knowledge and research shortages, and create original research ideas (Ampah et al., 2021).

Bibliometric research has become more prevalent in recent years inside the field of economics and related disciplines (Bonilla et al., 2015; Wei, 2019; Wang et al., 2020; Bahoo et al., 2021; Costa et al., 2023). Previous studies have looked at the bibliometric patterns of specific econometric tools. While Lam et al. (2023) focused on Granger causality studies running from 1981 to 2023, Liu and Li (2018) conducted a bibliometric study of spatial econometric research. Tantular et al. (2022) did a bibliometric study of the quantile regression model used on longitudinal data. So far, though, no bibliometric study has been done on QQR. A bibliometric study of QQR, a growing technique in time series econometrics, would offer a comprehensive picture of this creative econometric tool. Understanding the trends in the use and development of QQR helps researchers to determine the path of the literature.

Additionally, analysing the impact measures of existing literature helps highlight the influence of QQR in contemporary research fields. Furthermore, examining citation patterns, publication trends across different journals, and collaboration networks provides insights into the dissemination and adoption of this methodology. Moreover, this paper does not confine itself solely to the bibliometric analysis of QQR. Instead, it also emphasises the extensions and improvements made to the QQR model since its inception. Outlining the improvements of QQR enables researchers to stay updated with the evolution of the QQR model. Furthermore, we shed light on the shortcomings of ongoing research practices concerning QQR methodology, which helps overcome challenges in research practices related to QQR methodology.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a general overview of QQR. Section 3, titled 'Bibliometric Analysis,' presents the results of our bibliometric dataset. In Section 4, 'Modifications of QQR,' we highlight the improvements made to the QQR model since its inception. Section 5, 'Shortcomings of Ongoing Research on QQR,' criticises some existing practices in applying QQR. Finally, we offer concluding remarks in the 'Conclusion' section.

2. QQR Model: An Overview:

As previously mentioned, the quantile-dependent relationship between variables is illustrated in the QQR model. This methodology examines how different quantiles of the independent variable affect different quantiles of the dependent variable. In this method, both the dependent and independent variables are decomposed according to their quantile distribution. For instance, if the total distribution of quantiles for variable x is decomposed, then in QQR, a total of x^2 coefficients can be identified, demonstrating how each independent variable's quantile influences the dependent variable's quantile.

Sim and Zhou (2015) were the innovators in employing this method to illustrate the impact of diverse quantiles of oil price shocks on various quantiles of US market returns. The authors assert that the various intensities of oil price shocks can influence stock returns variably depending on prevailing market conditions. A significant negative or positive oil price shock may differentially affect a bear or bull market.

To develop a QR model, one must initially utilise quantile regression. Quantile regression, introduced by Koenker and Basset (1978), analyses the influence of the independent variable on various quantiles of the dependent variable inside the QR model.

$$y_t = \Phi^\tau(x_t) + \varepsilon_t^\tau \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), y_t is the dependent variable at t period of time. x_t signifies an independent variable at t period of time. τ epitomizes a specific quantile of y_t , while ε_t^τ is the residual. $\Phi^\tau(\cdot)$ is an unknown link function that is estimated.

To understand the quantile dependence between y_t and x_t , we linearise the unknown link function $\Phi^\tau(\cdot)$ around x^φ in equation (1) by employing a Taylor expansion. Hence, equation (1) can be expressed as:

$$\Phi^\tau(x_t) \approx \Phi^\tau(x^\varphi) + \Phi^{\tau'}(x^\varphi)(x_t - x^\varphi) \quad (2)$$

The partial derivative of $\Phi^\tau(x_t)$ is symbolized by $\Phi^{\tau'}$. To develop the QQR equation, equation (2) can be written as equation (3) (Sim & Zhou, 2015).

$$y_t = \Phi_0(\tau, \varphi) + \Phi_1(\tau, \varphi)(x_t - x^\varphi) + \varepsilon_t^\tau \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) is the equation for a QQR model where quantile dependence between dependent and independent variables is shown.

2. Bibliometric analysis:

2.1. Data and Methodology:

The bibliometric data utilised in this study was sourced from the Web of Science database. Related documents were designated from the database utilising terms such as 'quantile-on-quantile regression,' 'quantile-on-quantile approach,' and 'QQR.' The research under consideration was published from 2015 through April 2024, coinciding with the introduction of the QQR methodology in 2015.

After the data was rigorously examined to exclude vital information, 271 papers from 92 sources—including journals and edited volumes—were selected. The 'bibliometrix' package in RStudio, as created by Aria and Cuccurullo (2017), was used for a thorough examination of this data. This package's natural interface allows researchers to do scientific mapping analysis on bibliometric data.

Results and Discussions:

2.1.1. Overview:

A eloquent analysis of noteworthy information regarding research on the QQR method from 2015 to 2024 is presented in Table 1. During this time, 271 research publications were published. Especially, the mean citation per paper is 31, which shows the great influence of

studies on the QQR approach. Among these publications, only 18 were single-authored, with the majority co-authored. Furthermore, the annual growth rate of research on QQR is 52.27%, demonstrating its increasing prominence in applied econometric research. Figure 1 illustrates the annual publication trend of research works on QQR regression. In 2015, only one paper was published on QQR methodology by the founder of the method, Sim and Zhou (2015). The following year, Sim (2016) published another paper on QQR. However, publications on QQR began to rise exponentially, peaking in 2023 with 98 research papers. By April 2024, 44 papers had already been published. Table 2 displays the top ten globally most cited articles on QQR. The original research paper claims the first position, where the QQR method was developed. Other highly cited articles explore various applications of QQR to different research problems. Figure 2 depicts the historiography of QQR literature, illustrating the evolution of the literature from 2015 to 2024 and how the earlier works influence the later work. The arrows in Figure 2 represent citation networks, aiding in understanding the interconnectedness of the literature.

Table 1: Descriptive analysis: Main information	
Timespan	2015-2024
Articles	271
Annual growth rate	52.27%
Average citation per document	31
Authors	648
Authors in single-authored documents	18
Co-authors per document	3.81
Source: the authors	

Figure 1: Annual scientific production
Source: the authors

Table 2: Most cited articles		
Title	Author	Citation
Oil prices, US stock return, and the dependence between their quantiles	Sim and Zhou (2015)	612

topics, with 24.81% of research work published in core economics fields. Additionally, environmental science-related studies widely utilise QQR, particularly in studies on the nexus between the environment and the economy. Moreover, the field of business finance also acknowledges the applicability of QQR.

The widespread use of QQR in environmental studies is further reflected in Table 4, which showcases the top journals publishing QQR-related research. The top four journals with the most QQR articles focus on studies examining the relationship between the environment and the economy. Among these, 'Environmental Science and Pollution Research' (ESPR) ranks first in publication volume, with 30 research papers published. Furthermore, ESPR also leads in impact measure, with an h-index of 15, indicating that at least 15 articles related to QQR in this journal have garnered at least 15 citations. However, regarding total citations, 'Energy Economics' claims the top spot with 1022 citations, while ESPR follows with 860 citations.

Bradford's Law in Library and Information Science posits that a few journals publish the most significant research in a particular field. Our bibliometric analysis confirms Bradford's Law, with six journals publishing the most relevant work in QQR (Figure 3). These journals serve as the core sources for QQR research, with ESPR ranking first among them, followed by 'Resource Policy,' 'Energy Economics,' and others.

Field	Documents published (in percentage)
Economics	24.81%
Environmental sciences	20.61%
Business finance	18.70%
Environmental studies	14.12%
Green sustainable science technology	12.60%
Source: the authors	

Sources	Number of articles
Environmental science and pollution research	30
Resource policy	21
Energy economics	16
Energy & environment	12
Finance research letter	10
Energy	8
Journal of cleaner production	8
North American journal of economics and finance	8
International journal of sustainable development and world ecology	7
International review of financial analysis	7
Source: the authors	

Figure 3: Core sources by Bradford’s law

Sources: the author

2.1.3. Authors’ and Institutions’ Productivity Analysis:

Table 5 showcases the top five authors in terms of the number of publications. Adebayo TS leads the list with 29 publications, followed by Kartal MT and Sharif A, ranking second and third with 19 and 16 articles, respectively. Regarding the h-index, Adebayo TS maintains the top position, with 16 articles cited at least 16 times (refer to Table 6). Other authors with the highest number of documents follow Adebayo TS regarding the h-index. However, at the fifth position, Gupta R (h-index=6) is replaced by Shabaz M with an h-index of 7.

Regarding total citations received, Sim N and Zhou A outperform other authors. Both authors have received significantly higher citations with fewer articles, enjoying the privilege of being the founders of the model. Sharif A, Khan SAR, and Bossman A follow the founders regarding total citations (see Table 7). Additionally, Lotka’s law (Lotka, 1926) has been applied to measure the scientific productivity of authors. Figure 4 illustrates the results of Lotka’s law, revealing that 76 per cent of authors have published only one document regarding QQR. As the number of authors increases, productivity falls, with only one author producing more than ten research articles regarding QQR.

Among institutions, Cyprus International University emerges as the most productive institution regarding the number of articles, with 47 publications. Lebanese American University and Universiti Utara Malaysia rank second and third with 33 and 27 articles, respectively. Figure 5 displays the publication trend of the top five institutions regarding the number of publications.

Table 5: Top authors in terms of number of publications	
Authors	Number of articles
Adebayo TS	29
Kartal MT	19
Sharif A	16
Bossman A	10
Gupta R	9
Source: the authors	

Table 6: Top authors with highest h-index	
Authors	h-index
Adebayo TS	16
Sharif A	13
Kartal MT	9
Bossman A	8
Shabaz M	7
Source: the authors	

Table 7: Number of citations received	
Authors	Number of citations
Sim N	265
Zhou A	255
Sharif A	59
Khan SAR	46
Bossman A	41
Source: the authors	

Figure 4: Lotka's Law
Source: The authors

Figure 5: Institution’s production over time
Source: The authors

2.1.4. Application of QQR on different topics:

In this subsection, we analyse the application of QQR to specific topics within different fields. Repeating keywords in abstracts identifies the areas where QQR is most frequently applied. Table 8 presents the keywords mentioned the highest number of times in abstracts. 'Energy' is the most frequently mentioned keyword, appearing 475 times, followed by 'renewable energy,' 'economic growth,' and 'crude oil.' The dominance of energy and environmental economics topics is evident in the application of QQR. However, research in the finance field, particularly on capital markets, has also been conducted. Studies on income inequality, financial inclusion, and economic policy uncertainty are noteworthy.

Keywords	Number of times mentioned
Energy	475
Renewable energy	131
Economic growth	127
Crude oil	78
Carbon emission	70
Energy consumption	70
Oil price	61
Stock returns	54
Sustainable development	51
Source: The authors	

The predominance of environmental economics and business finance is further reflected in Figure 6, which illustrates the co-occurrence network among keywords. The co-

Figure 7: Trend of published documents by each country
Source: the author.

Figure 8: Countries' scientific production
Source: The authors

Table 9 reflects the total citation and average citation per document received by countries. China ranks first in total citations received, while its average citation per document is relatively low at 32.10. Conversely, although only 37 articles have been published in Lebanon, the average citation per article is 238.5, placing Lebanon first in terms of average citation received per article. Similarly, despite only 32 research articles being published in the United Kingdom, the average citation per article is as high as 178.7. Tunisia has published 16 articles with an average citation of 98.7.

On the other hand, for countries with one of the highest publications, such as Turkey, India, and Pakistan, their average citation per document is relatively low compared to other countries. Turkey, India, and Pakistan have average citations of 26.7, 13.3, and 21, respectively.

Table 9: Citation received by countries

Country	Total citation	Average article citation
China	3426	32.10
Malaysia	732	91.50
United Kingdom	536	178.70
Lebanon	477	238.50
Tunisia	296	98.70

Source: The authors

Regarding research collaboration, the highest number of collaborations occurred between China and Pakistan, with 31 articles featuring collaboration. The collaboration between Pakistan and Malaysia ranks second, with 23 articles published in collaboration. China-Malaysia and China-India collaborations rank third and fourth, with 17 and 13 research collaborations, respectively. Additionally, 13 research collaborations were conducted between China and the United Kingdom. Figure 9 displays the collaboration network on a world map.

Figure 9: Collaboration among countries
Source: the authors

3. Modification on QQR:

The robustness and implementation of the original QQR model, which was initially introduced by Sim and Zhou (2015), have been enhanced by numerous authors over time. The initial QQR model was distinguished by a bivariate specification and a single dependent variable. Nevertheless, this univariate approach prompted concerns regarding potential omitted variable bias. In order to circumvent this limitation, recent research has introduced a multivariate definition of the QQR model, which has increased the bivariate structure. In 2023, Sinha et al. devised a multivariate QQR model by incorporating a moderator exogenous variable. This research investigated the moderating effects of unemployment, company confidence, and economic policy uncertainty on the relationship between renewable energy

generation and green finance in the United States. Alola et al. (2023), Das et al. (2023), and Ozkan et al. (2023) are additional notable studies that have employed the multivariate specification of QQR and compared the results to conventional bivariate QQR, each of these studies were published in 2023.

The QQR model's robustness was not assessed by Sim and Zhou (2015). Over time, though, a new approach has developed in which the QQR model's robustness is judged by contrasting its coefficients with those of conventional quantile regression. Researchers either compute the Pearson correlation coefficient between QQR's average coefficients and those of quantile regression or compare the two sets of average coefficients to determine robustness (Depren et al., 2023; Kartal et al., 2023).

An additional minor contribution to the QQR literature is the use of visualisation techniques to demonstrate asymmetric effects. Sim and Zhou (2015) utilised 3-dimensional surface plots, whereas Hassan et al. (2021) presented 2-dimensional contour plots, offering an effective visual method for the analysis of coefficients. Furthermore, research has integrated various quantile-based econometric methodologies, including quantile unit root tests, quantile Granger causality tests, and quantile cointegration tests, to augment the contributions of studies primarily utilising QQR (Dagar & Malik, 2023; Adebayo et al., 2023).

The QQR methodology is a relatively new approach to macro econometric research that has not yet reached the age of ten years. Recent beginnings of major changes to this approach show its early stage of growth. In the future, more improvements to this model are to be anticipated.

3.1.1. Inadequacies of ongoing research on QQR:

There are numerous inadequacies in the ongoing research on the application of QQR that need to be rectified.

Firstly, while the multivariate QQR is now being used in the literature, its usage remains limited. Even after introducing the multivariate QQR, most studies still rely on the bivariate QQR structure. These studies are prone to omitted variable bias.

Secondly, a crucial shortcoming of QQR lies in its application to particular research questions. Sim and Zhou (2015) introduced this model to illustrate the quantile-based asymmetric relationship between stock returns and oil price shocks. In their study, both variables were stationary data with high frequency, making it feasible to show the relationship between different combinations of quantiles of distributions. For example, suppose both variables are decomposed into 19 parts based on their quantile of distribution from 0.5 to 0.95. In that case, it is feasible to show how different quantiles of oil price shocks affect different quantiles of stock returns. Such a combination is practical when both variables are stationary with high frequency; however, for low-frequency datasets with specific trends, combinations of all quantiles of distribution between variables may not be possible. For instance, Mallick et al. (2019) investigated the impact of different quantiles of per capita income (PCI) on various quantiles of carbon emissions (CE) in BRICS countries from 1980 to 2014. However, in countries like India and China, both PCI and CE exhibit an upward trend over this period. Consequently, it becomes practically infeasible to observe quantile combinations involving the lowest quantile of PCI and the highest quantile of CE (or vice versa) because both variables increased over time. Figure 10 and 11 depict the trends of PCI and CE from 1980 to 2014. Notably, when PCI is at its lowest quantile, CE also tends to be at its lowest quantile. Thus, quantile combinations between the lowest and highest quantiles of PCI and CE are highly

improbable. This limitation extends to other quantile combinations between these variables that are practically unattainable. Despite this challenge, statistical software gives results of QQR estimates of such infeasible quantile combinations. However, such results are deemed unreliable. Therefore, while QQR may be suitable for analysing high-frequency stationary data, it is unsuitable for datasets exhibiting deterministic trends.

Figure 10: PCI of China at constant USD

Source: Our world in data

Figure 11: CE of China in billions of tonnes

Source: Our world in data

Thirdly, another significant limitation of current practices in research on Quantile Quantile Regression (QQR) is the complete absence of reporting p-values for the coefficients. In QQR, when both variables are decomposed x times, a total of x^2 coefficients are obtained in matrix form. However, in regression analysis, determining whether a coefficient is significant at a specific confidence interval is a crucial aspect that should be reported. Surprisingly, many influential and highly cited works, such as Sim and Zhou (2015), Bouri et al. (2017), Selmi et al. (2018), and Meo and Karim (2022), fail to report p-values. While studies in QQR often present results through three-dimensional surface plots, including p-values is equally essential.

Furthermore, since QQR is a relatively recent methodology, popular statistical software packages do not offer dedicated tools for estimating QQR models. In software like RStudio, QQR is typically estimated using customised approaches, such as the 'quantreg' package and the 'locally polynomial quantile regression' ('lprq') function. However, utilising 'lprq' for QQR estimation requires advanced coding expertise, which limits its accessibility. Consequently, applying QQR in research papers remains confined to a select group of scholars. Despite its potential for high impact in the research area, only 271 research papers have been published on QQR. Therefore, there is a pressing need to develop dedicated packages in statistical software that would streamline the estimation process for QQR, thus making it more accessible to researchers.

4. Conclusion:

This study analysed the bibliometric trends, advancements, and shortcomings of an emerging econometric method, QQR. Our findings indicate that most QQR studies are conducted within environmental economics, resource economics, energy economics, and business and finance disciplines. Additionally, we identified critical seminal and influential works, measured their impact, and examined collaboration and co-occurrence networks of research themes. Moreover, our study outlines the evolution of the QQR model over time. We emphasise that the multivariate specification of the QQR model represents a significant recent development in the methodology. Furthermore, minor extensions, such as including robustness checks and different types of plots, have been incorporated into the QQR model. Moreover, we also highlight several challenges facing current practices in QQR research. Addressing these shortcomings is essential for achieving more robust results when applying QQR. In summary, our comprehensive examination of bibliometric trends, advancements, and challenges surrounding QQR provides valuable insights for researchers seeking to utilise the QQR technique more effectively.

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